

MACHINE LEARNING DATASETS FOR CYBER SECURITY APPLICATIONS

M.Eng. Nilă C. PhD. Student¹, Prof. Eng. Patriciu V. V. PhD.¹, Prof. Eng. Bica I. PhD.¹
 Computer Science Department – Military Technical Academy “Ferdinand I”, Romania¹
 ctinnil@protonmail.com

Abstract: *The main objective of this study is not to identify the best machine learning model, but instead to review the main datasets, publicly available, used to train and test security solutions that employ modern classification algorithms for anomaly detection. Hence, DARPA 1998 and KDD were studied as they were the first initiatives taken in this direction, while NSL-KDD, ISCXIDS2012 and CICIDS2017 are taken in consideration for future research because of their advantages. Personalized datasets will always bring a reasonable amount of uncertainty, especially since some feature vectors used for training remain unknown. Nevertheless, training on data specific to the protected infrastructure is more efficient, from the security point of view, than training on old attack signatures.*

Keywords: CYBER SECURITY, MACHINE LEARNING, DATASETS, INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEMS

1. Introduction

Today's IT&C infrastructures present a huge range of interconnected systems and devices, from multiple vendors, that may or may not operate with each other. This interconnection and the mixture of technology makes the update and maintenance process extremely difficult for organizations, opening up many opportunities for malicious actors.

According to [1], attackers usually seek to access, change or destroy sensitive information, obtain financial gain from users, or interrupt normal organizational processes, taking advantage of the load on SOC or CSIRT/CERT personnel, which is overwhelmed by the complexity and range of logging and reporting styles employed by various security solutions.

Moreover, there are many entities, with an online presence, that lack such a department or have their SOC staff engaged in other administrative tasks, like patch management and software updates. Classic security solutions like IDS/IPS systems, firewalls, proxies and antivirus software are not enough when presented with the task of protecting modern networks, that take advantage of new technology like IoT and 5G to process and transport terabytes of data every day.

Effective measures reduce the risk for organizations that have a full and real view of their infrastructure and do not perceive this task as mandatory routine, but as a way to reduce cost and increase quality of service.

Solutions that use machine learning algorithms to ease in the operator, highlighting the most important aspects of the available data, are more and more popular. In this context, we reviewed the most common datasets used for IDS solutions and analyzed the more recent approaches in generating new ones.

2. Prerequisites and means for solving the problem

There are many elements that influence the performance of a machine learning system, one of the most important ones, besides the algorithm itself and the methods used for characteristic extraction, being the quantity and quality of training data. [2]

Generally speaking, the values used in machine learning processes are usually generated from real data collected over a period of time. From these datasets, experts extract vectors of features that describe classes of the observed elements. [3] Publicly available datasets usually come as sets of features vectors, but they can also be available as traffic captures, log files or other types of formats.

These collections tend to lose their value over time, since technologies change and attacks evolve. As a result, researchers are confronted with old, incomplete data for the training and testing process of their machine learning algorithms for security solutions.

One option is to focus on current attacks and the observed IoCs. This and the most common datasets used in research will be discussed further on.

3. Solution of the examined problem

This paper will not only review the classic DARPA dataset developed by the MIT Lincoln Laboratory, KDD Cup 99, NSL-KDD and CTU-13, but also discuss some of the new approaches in dataset creation methodology.

DARPA 1998 IDS Dataset is one of the oldest sets being used in cyber security. The set was developed in March 1998 within the MIT Lincoln Laboratory under the coordination of the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency and the Air Force Research Laboratory in United States, and it has been subsequently supplemented with new data in 1999 and 2000.

The DARPA IDS dataset contains all network interactions and the entire contents of the data packets recorded in *tcpdump* format. The evaluated data is presented in several formats: traffic captures, Solaris BSM files, Windows NT audit files (in case of DARPA 1999), and files that contain the current processes. The target network consisted of a mixture of real and simulated systems, that also generated background traffic. The attacks were carried out only on the real systems. [4]

The data is split over nine weeks, seven for training and two for testing, but the records are not consistent. On the first day of the 4th week, the *tcpdump* capture is missing due to a technical error, and if the files size or the number of attacks is analyzed, we can observe an amplification in the activity towards the end of the experiment.

It can be considered that an approach that aims at the evolution of attacks over time can bring significant benefits to the efficiency of a machine learning algorithm.

In [5] it is highlighted that the data contained in this set does not have equal proportions, which makes a machine learning system bias, observable while applying a simple baseline algorithm such as ZeroR.

As a summarization, the DARPA set presents multiple limitations that may interfere with the model training process, like an unrealistic attack design and the impossibility to validate false-negative alerts. [6]

The KDD Cup99 set is an improvement but still inherits many of the DARPA IDS dataset flaws. This set was designed for use in the third edition of the International Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining Tools competition, part of the fifth International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining. [7]

The set is composed out of a complete standardized list of feature vectors, that display attacks from four main categories, recorded in a military architecture network: Denial-of-Service attacks, Remote to User attacks, User to Root attacks and probing.

The KDD dataset is nothing more than the result of the processed DARPA dataset. The gigabyte traffic captures used for training were transformed in approximative five million series of vectors, that describe the network events. Similarly, the test data was represented in a series consisting of two million vectors.

A feature vector is a sequence of values that describe a TCP connection that begins and ends at well-defined time, including data flows to and from a source IP address to a destination IP address, using a certain protocol. Each vector is labeled either normal or attack, specifying the type of attack.

The data sets contain a total of 24 types of attacks for training, and only validations for the test subset. Although the training set contains 4,889,431 records each with 41 features, only 1,074,992 are unique, some of the vectors being duplicated tens of times. The test set has redundant values as well; out of a total of 2,984,154, only 576,449 records being unique (see Fig. 1).

Using this duplicate data in both training and testing processes may result in biased machine learning algorithms, that promote certain predictions more often than others just due to its chance of occurrence.

Fig. 1 - The proportions of duplicate data in KDD Cup99

Moreover, the *num_outbound_cmds* feature always has a value of 0, both in the training and testing data, which makes it dispensable in creating a machine learning algorithm and there for can be ignored or removed from the set.

By removing this feature, throw out the process of feature engineering we can improve the accuracy of the machine learning algorithms applied [8].

However, KDD Cup99 was the most used set between 2000-2012 [9], being employed in countless experiments, regardless of its disadvantages, as presented by Tavallae et.al. in [10].

The data set is no longer used internationally due to the numerous criticisms raised by the community involved in IDS development and also because it is no longer an exact model of modern networks. Nevertheless, KDD Cup99 remains a minimum test that new solutions need to pass so that they can be taken into account as machine learning based IDSs.

To solve most of the problems mentioned above, a new set was developed within the University of New Brunswick, Canada, based on KDD, hence the name NSL-KDD. The advantages broth in by this set are presented by Laheeb et.al. in [11] as follows:

- it does not include redundant records in the train set, so the classifiers will not be biased towards more frequent records;
- it does not include duplicate records in the proposed test sets, so the performance of the systems is not influenced by the records frequency, but by the methods which have better detection rates;
- the number of selected records from each difficulty level is inversely proportional to the percentage of records in the original KDD dataset.

NSL-KDD datasets presents the same main types of attack as KDD 99. The total number of individual attacks is comparable with the number of normal instances.

Even though this new version of KDD set still presents some problems and it does not perfectly represent a real network, NSL-KDD is one of the most used datasets for training ML-IDS applications. This set was employed by researchers during 2009

mostly because of the reasonable number of records from both training and testing and the lack of public available data.

This feature gives the researcher the possibility to run experiments on the complete set, without having to select a random portion of it, offering coherence to the results obtained.

In 2015 L. Dhanabal et.al. analyzed and presented the four types of attacks described by NSL-KDD dataset, highlighting the fact that most vulnerable services lay under the TCP protocol (see Fig. 2) and they are heavily exploited through DoS attacks. [12] This particular aspect of the NSL-KDD dataset it is not as significant as it seems, typically because DoS attacks require a huge number of packages for their success and hence the weight of these attacks is not comparable to the other three.

Fig. 2 - Attack types proportions in NSL-KDD

The main reason why NSL-KDD is so popular in the IDS development community, is the lack of public data suitable for training of such solutions.

There are a lot of machine learning algorithms developed by different entities, with the unique purpose of outdoing each other in performance. These algorithms are based on mathematical techniques, such as decision trees, linear programming and so on and strive to identify the most appropriate predictive model.

The WEKA framework was used to evaluate this set, because of its vast library machine learning algorithms and the ability to automate the learning and testing process. The platform is used by numerous researchers in their activity. The instruments available can be split in the following categories: preparation, classification, regression, grouping and the visualization of data. [13]

The cross-validation method with 10 folds was used for the initial phase of the experiment, thus the objective consisted in identifying an appropriate dataset for future machine learning security solutions and not the trained model itself. The cross-validation method involves repeated retentions of a certain percentage of the training data for the testing phase, resulting in a mean of subsequent precisions.

The cross-validation method is a useful mechanism to evaluate the effectiveness of machine learning models, especially because it combats the phenomenon of overfitting and underfitting. Furthermore, this method is practical in the identification process of hyper model parameters, as these will result in a minimal test error.

J48 represents the most common training technique for IDS systems with machine learning according to many scientific papers and currently one of the best algorithms. This algorithm was introduced for the first time by Breiman et.al. in the book [14]. J48 produces a binary frame and classifies any new item based on a decision tree constructed from the attributes of the training data. Whenever a new training set is introduced, this algorithm precisely recognizes the attribute that have more influence over the result, thus they have more weight. The decision tree is recursively spanned until the training data is perfectly classified to ensure a maximum accuracy on the testing data.

Moreover, specialists consider that support-vector-machine (SVM) algorithms and random forests work better in security applications in which it is important to identify anomalies.

SVM is a very popular algorithm, which presents the advantage that it can be used for both linear and nonlinear classification. The algorithm can be described in the form of a separation line (a decision plan) which divides the objects into two subsets so that in each subset all the elements are similar. However, this principle is applicable only when dividing between malicious and normal events as in the case of NSL-KDD, making it more difficult to operate when trying to identify different attack types. This makes SVM much slower than J48 and less precise.

Also, considering the lessons learned from previous sets, the features can be engineered and some of them even eliminated since they don't influence the precision of the algorithm. Among the features that can be eliminated since they don't influence significant changes are: *num_outbound_cms*, *is_host_login*, *land* and *is_guest_login*.

Table 1 – Comparison of tested algorithms on NSL-KDD dataset

Algorithm	Precision (on the remaining 37 features)	Observations
ZeroR	53,46 %	Baseline
OneR	96,37 %	Using only the <i>src_bytes</i> feature
NaiveBayes	90,39 %	
SVM	97,40 %	
J48	99,78 %	
RandomForest	99,92 %	Most accurate on default parameters.

The values above indicate that simple algorithms work well, and these should always be tried first to identify baseline values useful for future comparison with more complex machine learning algorithms. Trying the simplest algorithms first becomes extremely useful when dealing with noisy datasets, such as the ones used in cyber security.

From the preliminary analysis and conclusions drawn from various scientific papers such as [15], [11] and [12], it can be assessed that NSL-KDD represents a good candidate for training IDS solutions with machine learning classifiers.

The sets developed after DARPA 1998 seem to have moved on from the original format that employed multiple sources of data for intrusion detection. Both KDD Cup99 and the improved NSL-KDD set present the data as feature vectors, while DARPA consists of a series of network traffic captures in *tcpdump* format, Solaris BSM and Windows NT logs and process lists extracted at certain time intervals.

Additionally, the form in which the data is presented, split on weekdays over nine weeks, evokes the current intelligent security and monitoring systems (SIEMs), which integrate and correlate data from multiple sources to identify patterns, not only highlighting individually events, but also their evolution over time.

There are other alternative IDS sets that employ network traffic captures as training and testing data, equally used by researchers in the academic community. These sets bring an alternative image to the development of IDS with machine learning algorithms.

One of this sets, publicly available is CTU-13, which contains thirteen tcpdump bot and background network traffic captures. The dataset has been developed within the Czech Technical University in Prague (abr. CTU) in 2011. [16]

The thirteen network captures consist of normal, unknown and traffic generated by seven types of bots: Neris, Rbot, Virut, Menti, Sogou, Murlo and NSIS.ay. Each one contains traffic specific to a single type of bot with sizes in the gigabytes range.

The first analysis of CTU-13 was published in [16] and it used unidirectional netflows to represent the traffic and to assign the

labels. This reference shouldn't be used for future studies since it has been exceeded by the second analysis of dataset, in which bidirectional netflows was used. Bidirectional netflows have more advantages than the unidirectional ones. First of all, bidirectional netflows fix the problem of differentiation between the client and server. Secondly, the second approach include more information, including detailed labels.

Each scenario in the dataset has been processed so that the output files have significant differences between them. For confidentiality reasons, the complete packet captures, which contained all the traffic, have not been made publicly available for researchers.

The fact that more than 90% of the data comprised of unknown background traffic, gives some uncertainty to the usability of this set.

The Cybersecurity Institute from the University of New Brunswick, Canada, have been developing two other datasets for IDS systems, as follows:

- intrusion detection evaluation dataset (ISCXIDS2012);
- intrusion detection evaluation dataset (CICIDS2017).

These two datasets were developed as a response to the need of a public and standard set for consistent evaluating of the anomaly detection rate in IDS and IPS systems.

The developers of these datasets have noticed the lack of adequate evaluation data, many of the sets not being public as they contain private data, or they are excessively anonymized. The public sets are short on statistical characteristics essential to the evaluation process. In addition, due to the permanent evolution of attack patterns, the need to change the approach was certain, leaving the static sets behind and adopting dynamic sets, that reflect the specific network dynamic at a defined time and can be extended, modified and reproduced. [17]

ISCXIDS2012 has been developed starting from the idea of drawing up some generic profiles, that should truly illustrate specific actions over different application protocols such as HTTP, SSH, FTP, SMTP, IMAP and POP3.

The profiles are played out by agents that mimic the normal behavior of their own users, permanently assisted by operators to avoid any unwanted action. In the same time different attack scenarios are running, emulating multiple malicious cyber actions.

The dataset developed by UNB presents the following features:

- realistic configuration, from the network point of view and the generated traffic;
- it is labeled, making it easy to use in machine learning solutions;
- the captures contained in this set are complete, bringing in all necessary data for different tests;
- the set describes modern attack scenarios. [18]

The CICIDS2017 dataset was developed on the same idea as the ISCXIDS2012, more exactly, the previous sets suffer from the lack of diversified data, some of them providing a low variety of known attacks, anonymized data and miss out important metadata.

Likewise, this dataset contains benign traffic combined with relevant attack patterns, represented in their pure form (PCAP files). Additionally, this packet captures were analyzed with their own solution, CICFlowMeter. This application exports the main features, like timestamp, IP addresses, source and destination ports, protocols and type of the attack in CSV format.

The data was collected over the course of five working days, similarly to other sets mentioned above, a particular aspect of the CICIDS2017 is that the Monday capture doesn't contain malicious traffic.

Benign traffic is generated using 25 user profiles that perform common tasks typical to normal operators, over HTTP, HTTPS,

FTP, SSH and email. The malicious traffic emulates brute force attacks both on FTP and SSH, DoS and DDoS, Heartbleed, botnet and another Web attacks.

Another important aspect is that the set has eighty characteristics, according to the authors making it an extremely explicit dataset, what may cause some generalization problems in the training process (overfitting). The files in the MachineLearningCVE package contain 79 features, the Fwd Header Length feature being duplicated. Definitely, some features can be ignored depending on their relevance and the bigger number could be considered an advantage since researchers have more wiggle room when engineering features.

CICIDS2017 dataset contains 2.830.744 records in the section dedicate to machine learning, with duplicate values, both for legitimate and malicious traffic. 80,30% out of the full dataset is labeled as normal traffic. If the unique records are analyzed, approximate 80,43% are in the normal class, that gives a certain consistency to the set.

It can be observed that there are two main approaches when discussing about proprietary machine leading dataset generation, one focusing on the network traffic generated by some malicious applications that run inside the observed network. The second approach, proposed in the present paper and the authors of the CICIDS2017 dataset, concentrates on the traffic that is observed at the border of the network, accentuating external threats. Regardless to say that the best would be to combine both methods.

4. Results and discussion

An alternative to the above-mentioned approaches could be a system consisting of a series of equipment exposed on the Internet, to many new automatic or manual attacks. The data recorded can be analyzed for the development of dynamic data sets. The system in question can be formed by multiple simple Linux boxes, capable of monitoring the activity on each port, using a simple iptables rule.

A better approach involves the use of one or more honeypot systems exposed on the Internet. This method emulates many vulnerable systems and services, which can be adapted to the needs of the beneficiary. A possible example is the use of specific IOT honeypot modules to monitor and alert on Mirai, VPNFilter or similar botnets activity. This approach also responds to a crucial ML system need, hence a sufficiently large set with specified classes and measurable features.

In relation to the for-mentioned research and the tested solutions it has been observed that some public sets focus strictly on the extracted characteristics; many modern solutions being able to run ML algorithms on events dispersed over time, considering certain patterns. By exploiting the data collected throughout honeypots, it is possible to detect patterns of certain malicious unknown entities and take automated actions to minimize the impact.

5. Conclusions

An option for training and testing security solutions would be to generate your own training dataset. The CICIDS2017 set is composed by generating different attack scenarios with Kali Linux or Windows attack machines, on Windows, Linux and Mac OS target systems.

This will fix the problems present in most current sets, that contain old attack signatures, but only for a short period of time. Each new set created will be affected by the passage of time and the emergence of new attack models, which will not be covered.

Another problem caused by the creation of a custom set is the dilemma of attribution, having to do with unknown or ambiguous events that cannot be considered attacks with certainty. Studies have proven that machine learning systems that use a small set of proper labeled data are more efficient than those without this feature. [19]

Semi-supervised training can be the answer, allowing the processing of only a small number of training vectors which are properly marked. This may be considered as a viable approach, since full autonomous systems may be targeted by attackers, and may misclassify malicious actions.

6. References

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